

DEEP LEARNING IN COOKING ENVIRONMENTS

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TABLE OF CONTENTS

Introduction

Deep Learning in Cooking Environments

Datasets & Methods

Results

Conclusions & Future work

AI & CV

In recent years, AI is experiencing monumental growth. For this reason, researchers and enthusiasts are working on numerous aspects of this field. One of these area is **computer vision**.

The goal of this field is to enable machines to **see the world and use knowledge as humans do**.

OBJECT DETECTION

The problem definition of object detection is to determine where objects are in each image (**object localization**) and which category belongs to each object (**object classification**)

Kitti dataset

Source: <https://www.cvlibs.net/datasets/kitti/>

DOTA dataset

Source: <https://captain-whu.github.io/DOTA/dataset.html>

DocLayNet

Source: <https://github.com/DS4SD/DocLayNet>

Model selection

Testing the model

DL IN COOKING ENVS

Nowadays, it is difficult to find any research that uses this technology to detect and recognize common household objects in realistic environments, even though it is one of the key factors for service robotics.

Computer vision in cooking environments shows that this technology is used for tasks such as cooking state recognition, collaborative cooking, and assistive cooking using augmented reality.

The main **objective** of this investigation is to develop a model that helps to **modify and improve the user experience** in the use of cooking appliances.

This study will show that by combining artificial vision with deep learning, further improvements in cooking automation, safety and energy efficiency can be achieved.

IDEA

It is desired to identify situations such as:

- 1 Presence or non-presence of utensils on lit hobs
- 2 Fire
- 3 Boiling and smoke
- 4 Presence of user manipulating the cookware
- 5 Good adjustmentg of the pot/pan size

SET-UP

kitchenware

camera 1

camera 2

Functional mock-up where the experiments have been carried out

Schematic diagram of lateral camera positioning

cooktop with Bluetooth connectivity

DATASET

“ The generated dataset must be representative of deployed environment. For real-world use cases we recommend images from different times of day, different seasons, different weather, different lighting, different angles, different sources (scraped online, collected locally, different cameras) etc. ” (source: <https://docs.ultralytics.com/yolov5>)

Object detection dataset classes: (a) Closed pots; (b) Open pots; (c) Pans; (d) Kitchenware; (e) User; and (f) Others.

EXAMPLES

The generated dataset contains more than **7500** labelled images

Examples of labelled images

DATA AUGMENTATION

Data augmentation is a technique of artificially increasing the training set by creating modified copies of a dataset using existing data.

image flipping

random brightness and contrast

CLASS DISTRIBUTION

RESULTS

The results do not vary considerably between the different architectures: the maximum difference between all the models is less than 1%

Model	Params (M)	Batch size	Precision	Recall	mAP 0.5	FPS	Inference time (ms)	Training time (h)
YOLOv5n	1.9	32	0.988	0.992	0.994	84	9.3	5.48
YOLOv6n	4.3	32	0.984	0.990	0.994	43	17.2	6.07
YOLOv5s	7.2	32	0.991	0.993	0.994	80	10.3	5.88
YOLOv6s	17.2	16	0.994	0.990	0.997	42	20.6	9.38
YOLOv5m	21.2	16	0.992	0.995	0.994	73	11.9	10.45
YOLOv6m	34.3	8	0.995	0.990	0.997	39	23.5	20.71
YOLOv7	36.9	16	0.992	0.992	0.997	61	15	15.15
YOLOv5l	46.5	8	0.993	0.996	0.994	61	14.7	17.48

WORKFLOW

Automatic detection of kitchen switch-on and Bluetooth connection

Kitchen BLE connection sequence. (a) Kitchen and BLE off; (b) Kitchen ON and connecting BLE; and (c) Kitchen and BLE ON.

Cooking states recognition + automatic cooktop regulation

Boiling situation identification. (a) Open pot with maximum power but without boiling; (b) Open pot with boiling; and (c) Open pot without boiling and power has been reduced.

Pan with oil identification. (a) Normal pan without oil; (b) Identification of pan with oil; and (c) Pan with oil and power has been increased.

Recommendation of the best kitchen heater

Example of a recommendation of the best kitchen heater. (a) Both pans can be repositioned; (b) The pan is in the right heater, but its position can be improved; and (c) The pans are perfectly placed.

User identification

(a)

(b)

User identification. (a) No user; and (b) User manipulating

Recognition of high amount of kitchenware

(a)

(b)

Example of high amount of kitchenware. (a) Good situation; and (b) Identification of high amount of kitchenware.

Example of detection of a heater with no cookware

Example of high amount of kitchenware. (a) Start situation of the example; (b) The algorithm has detected that a heater is ON without cookware; (c) The command to switch OFF the heater is sent; and (d) The burner is OFF.

Testing the algorithm under different light conditions & different image cropping

(a)

(b)

(c)

(d)

Developed algorithm under different light conditions. (a) Wider and lighter framing; (b) Wider framing and less light; (c) Wider framing and low light; and (d) Lighter and tighter framing.

CONCLUSIONS

First time DL to automatically control the cooktop

Good performance under different scenarios

YOLOv5 is good and fast for the application

Future work involves deploying the algorithm in a low-cost device (Coral, MCU...)

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** Some of the images have been generated with Leonardo AI **

THANK YOU

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